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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BESS	Battery Energy Storage Systems
CHIL	Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop
CHP	Combine Heat and Power
CSC	Centralized Supervisory Controller
CVC	Coordinated Voltage Control
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DG	Distributed Generation
DHN	District Heating Network
DRTS	Digital Real-Time Simulator
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DuI	Domain under Investigation
EHP	Electrical Heat Pump
ESS	Energy Storage Systems
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
FMU	Functional Mock-up Unit
FRT	Fault-Ride-Through
FuI	Function(s) under Investigation
FuT	Functions under Test
GB	Great Britain
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
GDS	Geographically Distributed Simulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HTD	Holistic Test Description
HUT	Hardware under Test
IA	Interface Algorithm
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
JRA	Joint Research Activity
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LPF	Low-Pass Filter
LV	Low Voltage
MIOB	Multi IO Box
MV	Medium Voltage
NA	Networking Activity
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OLTC	On-Load Tap Changer
OuI	Object under Investigation
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PoI	Purpose of Investigation
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
PV	Photovoltaic
QA	Quality Attributes
QS-PHIL	Quasi-Static Power Hardware-in-the-Loop

RI	Research Infrastructure
RIasC	Research Infrastructure as Code
RTDS	Real-Time Digital Simulator
SISO	Single-Input Single-Output
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SoC	State of Charge
SPoF	Single Point of Failure
SuT	System under Test
TCR	Test Criteria
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion
TM	Target Metrics
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VA	Variability Attributes
V-ITM	Voltage-Type Ideal Transformer Model
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VSIDC	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation
WAN	Wide Area Network
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The advanced methods and services developed within the ERIGrid 2.0 project to realize extended research infrastructure capabilities, as part of WP11-JRA2 and WP12-JRA3, are intended to be integrated and demonstrated within WP13-JRA4. This document presents the work undertaken as part of the test case description task.

The objectives of this task are three-fold: (i) to derive a set of test cases for effective demonstration of the developed advanced methods and services, (ii) to propose a tentative timeline for their implementation, and (iii) to develop a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the extended research infrastructure capabilities realized through the developed advanced methods and services.

The document first presents the methodology for the down selection of the advanced methods and services taken forward as demonstrations within the JRA4 WP. An effective demonstration is enabled by linking each chosen method and service with a test case defined within WP NA4. A number of methods and services were combined to down-select five demonstrations to be taken forward. The demonstrations are documented through the use of Holistic Test Description (HTD) template, comprising the test description, test specification and experiment specification. Tentative timelines for the implementation of the demonstrations are drawn with concrete tasks identified for their realization. Questionnaires aiming at evaluating KPIs for the assessment of the advanced methods and services are developed: a generic set of questionnaires applicable to all the demonstrations identified, followed by demonstration-specific questionnaires for each of the demonstrations.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This report documents the shortlisted set of advanced methods and services used as demonstrations within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Presenting the methodology adopted for downselecting a set of advanced methods and services, the demonstrations are documented in the form of Holistic Test Case descriptions. In addition, the report also presents a set of KPIs in the form of a questionnaire, developed to evaluate the performance of the extended capabilities of the Research Infrastructure (RI).

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organized as follows: Section 1 presents the purpose and scope of the deliverable, Section 2 introduces the objectives of JRA4.1 and elaborates the methodology adopted for the development of a detailed plan for the implementation of the demonstrations. An overview of JRA2 and JRA3 developments is presented in Section 3, which provides context moving for the description of the demonstrations. A brief description of the finalized demonstrations is documented in Section 4, while the detailed HTD template for each demonstration is individually documented in the appendices. Section 5 is dedicated to the development of KPIs to evaluate the extended capabilities of the RIs; this section describes the process adopted for the derivation of the KPIs. Conclusions are reported in Section 6. Finally, demonstration HTD descriptions for the five selected test cases are provided in Appendix 1 to Appendix 5.

2 Scope and Organization of Work

2.1 Overview of the Work Package

The main objective of the Joint Research Activity (JRA)4 Work Package (WP), “Integration and Demonstration of Services in the Extended Research Infrastructure”, is to demonstrate the advanced methods and services developed in ERIGrid 2.0 to realize extended RI capabilities. The JRA4 comprises four tasks:

- Task JRA4.1 - Test Cases Definition
- Task JRA4.2 - Implementation of the Tools for the RIs Integration and Automation
- Task JRA4.3 - Demonstrations of the Services in the Extended RIs
- Task JRA4.4 - Evaluation of the Services in the Extended RIs

The first task is responsible for defining the test cases that will demonstrate the advanced methods and services developed within the project, the second task is responsible for the implementation of any dependencies within the participating RIs to allow for the demonstrations to be undertaken, while the third task is where the demonstrations are undertaken. The fourth task is responsible to analyse the outcomes of the results from task three and articulate the clear benefits of RIs integration achieved.

2.2 Objectives of the Task

Four distinct objectives for JRA4.1 have been identified within the description of work as summarized below:

- Down selection of advanced methods and services developed as part of JRA2 and JRA3 for the demonstration of extended RI capabilities.
- Defining effective demonstrations that substantiate the extended capabilities realized through the advanced methods and services. These are realized by combining advanced methods and services for their utilization within the context of a representative smart grid scenario.
- Documenting the defined demonstrations using the HTD template. This includes the identification of partners, the RIs involved and a detailed timeline of its implementation running up to JRA4.3.
- Defining a set of KPIs for the evaluation of the implemented extended RI capabilities.

2.3 Methodology

JRA4 brings together the advanced methods developed within JRA2, the services to be developed within JRA3, the test cases defined within Networking Activity (NA)4 and the benchmark networks developed within JRA1 to define an effective demonstration. The methodology adopted for the definition of the demonstrations is presented in Figure 1.

First, by means of a workshop with the participating members of JRA4.1, the feasibility of demonstrating the developments of JRA2 in the context of smart grid scenarios was discussed.

Figure 1: Illustration of a detailed plan for the development.

The test cases developed as part of NA4 served as a good reference, providing several contextual smart grid scenarios readily. A number of developments were identified as potential candidates for demonstration.

Then the suitability of benchmarks developed within JRA1 has been assessed. The electrical and multi-energy benchmarks were identified as potential candidates. However, the two benchmarks were not suitable for direct adoption by all potential demonstrations. In some cases, the benchmarks were adapted and in some cases, simpler setups were utilized. The third stage involved an assessment of the services that will be required to support the demonstrations. Although a number of services had already been identified, this exercise helped further refine the requirements of the services under development.

The fourth stage involved the consolidation of the development, scenario, and services into a demonstration through the use of the HTD template. This resulted in the development of five demonstrations.

At the same time, another subgroup of participants not involved in the test case development worked on the development of KPIs that will be used to assess the extended RI capabilities. The same subgroup will evaluate the KPIs in the JRA4.4 when the demonstration will be completed.

3 Overview of Advanced Methods and Services

In this section, a brief overview of the advanced methods developed within JRA2 and the services in development within JRA3 are presented. This will allow the readers to follow the demonstrations defined later in Section 4.

3.1 JRA2.1 Developments

Task JRA2.1 aims at evolving a standards-based, open simulation framework integrating simulators which do not share a common time base, either because the relevant subsystem dynamics are in different time scales, or because of the need to integrate time-continuous and event-based simulators.

3.1.1 Integration of Continuous and Event-driven Systems

In most smart grid applications, the primary feature of interest of information technology/communication networks is the – often variable and possibly unpredictable – delay they introduce into control applications. They are discrete, event-driven systems that are modelled using approaches such as queuing theory. In the same context, Alternating Current (AC) power systems are modelled as continuous-time systems and are often simulated using a fixed-time step simulator. A co-simulation using such entities with fundamentally different time bases is a challenging task, not the least because of the lack of support in standardized co-simulation interfaces. As a result, many AC/Information and Communication Technology (ICT) co-simulation setups are ad-hoc, single-purpose developments tuned for one particular application. The Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) standard (*FMI for Model Exchange, Co-Simulation, and Scheduled Execution*, 2022) has gained dedicated support for event-driven systems in its recently released version 3.0. This track builds onto the new version of the standard to develop a multi-purpose co-simulation platform with the following development steps:

1. Development of a FMI 3.0 compliant test Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU) for simple communication network simulation, modelled as a single pipeline with variable delay.
2. Implementation of a Python wrapper for FMI 3.0 FMUs to simplify the integration with a Python-based co-simulation environment.
3. Application of the simple FMU in a closed-loop control test case using the MOSAIK 3.0 co-simulation master (*mosaik*, 2022). The test case is adopted from previous work in the ERIGrid project (*Deliverable D-JRA2.2: Smart Grid ICT assessment method*, 2018) where a proof-of-concept was demonstrated highlighting the lack of capabilities in the previous (2.0) version of the FMI standard.
4. Extension of the previously tested FMU into an arbitrary network with multiple inputs and outputs.
5. Connection of a dedicated communication simulator instead of the test FMU.

3.1.2 Integration of Continuous Systems with Different Time Scales

Despite the substantial synergies possible from sector coupling between electrical and heat networks, the operation of AC grids and district heating networks today constitutes two entirely

separate ecosystems, each with its own procedures and toolchains. Consequently, simulation-based technical assessment of multi-energy grids where the main focus is on issues related to grid operation and control remains a challenge due to the lack of generic, domain-integrated tools. The main issue is a lack of open-source heat network simulators and the significant difference in the relevant time scales (dynamic effects in the heat domain occur at time scales which can be considered steady-state in electrical networks). This track has aimed to improve the situation through the following developments:

1. Extension of the Python pandapipes package (*pandapipes*, 2022) to perform quasi-dynamic heat distribution simulations which compute dynamic temperature flows based on the steady-state hydraulic mass flow calculations in pandapipes, but considering the thermal inertia of the system.
2. Extension of the Modelica DisHeatLib library (*DisHeatLib*, 2019) to include a heat pump model that is adequate for use in a co-simulation with a power grid.
3. Development of a co-simulation setup using the above components and based on the JRA1 multi-energy network benchmark case.

3.1.3 Co-simulation Initialisation

A lack of “out-of-the-box” solutions is still one of the obstacles in the way of wider adoption of co-simulation tools in the smart energy domain. A particular challenge in this context is the configuration, invocation and generic initialization of larger-scale co-simulation setups. This includes heuristics for the automatic resolution of algebraic loops (i.e., the automatic determination of simulator executing order) and for the determination of coherent starting values for algebraic and state variables across the co-simulation, including the internal state of individual simulators as well as the coupling variables between the simulators. The following aspects are under development in this track:

1. Assessment and categorization of configuration and initialization issues experienced by consortium members in past and related research.
2. Proof-of-Concept of a loop resolution method based on superdense time (same-time loops), using the multi-energy benchmark case from JRA1.
3. Functional extension of the mosaik 3.0 co-simulation master in order to support the above loop resolution method.

3.2 JRA2.2 Developments

Task JRA2.2 involves the assessment and development of novel real-time coupling solutions and Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) approaches. The development and research progress of each track are summarized below.

3.2.1 Time Delay Compensation and Bandwidth Estimation

Time delay, as an inherent characteristic of a Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) (Guillo-Sansano, Syed, Roscoe, Burt, & Coffele, 2021) and Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation (GDRTS) setups (Syed et al., 2021), not only degrades the closed-loop stability but also deteriorates the simulation accuracy and power transfer transparency between the

interconnected subsystems (Feng et al., 2021). This track looks at developing compensation methods to alleviate the negative impact of time delay on the stability and accuracy of the GDRTS systems. The following three aspects are under development:

1. A comprehensive assessment of the synchronization performance of industrial clocks regarding their ability to synchronize two geographically distributed RIs and their precision in determining the time delay between them.
2. A network monitoring tool able to measure the delays between the interconnected RIs is being developed through the implementation of the time delay logging units across the RIs. One-way latency and round-trip latency can be determined by measuring a packet of data transmitted from one RI to another.
3. A statistical or artificial intelligence-based approach is under development to estimate time delays between RIs. The statistical delay data is the foundation for the development of time delay compensation for geographically distributed RIs.

3.2.2 Improving Stability and Accuracy of HIL Simulation

Stability and accuracy issues arising from the employment of an interface comprising a power amplifier, signal conversion units, etc., in a PHIL or GDRTS system pose a significant threat to the robustness and fidelity of real-time simulations. This track aims at assessing the conventional schemes proposed to enhance the PHIL stability and accuracy in the literature (Lauss & Strunz, 2019; Lauss & Strunz, 2021; Feng et al., 2021; Kotsampopoulos, Lehfuss, Lauss, Bletterie, & Hatziargyriou, 2015). To mitigate the impact of non-ideal characteristics of the power interface on the stability and accuracy, this track develops advanced interface algorithms to enhance the stability and accuracy of the PHIL and GDRTS. The following aspects are either achieved or under development:

1. Literature review, investigation, and simulation-based validation of the conventional PHIL stabilization schemes have been undertaken to contextualize the problem statement and to support the development of novel interface algorithms and approaches.
2. The stability and accuracy of the GDRTS setup based on synchronous and asynchronous coupling methods are analyzed.
3. A virtual shifted impedance and time delay compensation-based interface has been proposed to enhance the stability and improve the accuracy of the PHIL setup.
4. Theoretical analysis, analytical assessment, and simulations have been performed to verify the proposed approach. Furthermore, preliminary experiment validation will be carried out to validate the effectiveness of the proposed interface.

3.2.3 Sensitivity Analysis based on Mathematical Modelling of PHIL Simulation Systems

A power interface consisting of a power amplifier, sensors, and signal conversion units is essential to bridge the real-time emulated system and the physical system under test. However, the use of the power interface inevitably introduces external disturbances including the sensor noise, switching harmonics, or quantization noise into the PHIL closed-loop setup. To quantitatively analyze and assess the impact of the external disturbances on the PHIL response, this track aims at identifying suitable methods to analyze the sensitivity properties of HIL simulation

systems and develop frameworks for the sensitivity analysis for the PHIL setup with different interfacing typologies. The development of this track is categorized as the followings:

1. A comprehensive review of the mathematical modelling principles for PHIL setup with different interfacing topologies has been undertaken.
2. Based on the classical control theory, detailed analytical modelling principles of the sensitivity analysis for the PHIL system along with a sensitivity analysis framework have been developed. The criteria for system stability or accuracy were discussed and based on this concept, system properties and related measures such as the phase margin, the gain margin, or the vector margin were introduced to the sensitivity analysis framework.
3. Based on the sensitivity analysis framework developed, analytical assessment and experimental validation of the PHIL system with voltage-type and current-type interfaces were undertaken.

3.2.4 Applicability of Different Real-time Methods for Validation

In a GDRTS setup, the data between the geographically distributed research infrastructure is transmitted by the internet and this attribute results in a large time delay in the closed-loop setup. As a key impacting factor on the stability and accuracy of the GDRTS, the impact of the large delay should be well analyzed and assessed before the final deployment of a GDRTS system. The configuration and the manner of signal conversion and signal transmission are dependent on the coupling approaches adopted in the GDRTS (Syed et al., 2021). Consequently, the stability analysis and assessment approaches should be adjustable according to the GDRTS coupling approaches. This track aims at developing stability analysis models for the GDRTS setup with different coupling configurations along with its applicability studies. The development of this track is summarized as follows:

1. The limitations of the conventional Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) stability analysis methods and their applicability for assessing the stability of GDRTS systems with different coupling approaches have been identified.
2. A small-signal stability analysis model for the stability analysis of the GDRTS with synchronous and asynchronous coupling methods has been developed.
3. The applicability of the proposed stability analysis model has been validated by establishing the stability boundaries for the selection coupling types for GDRTS setups with regard to different impacting factors.
4. A guide aiming at providing detailed step-by-step instruction in setting up GDRTS-based experiments is being developed.

3.2.5 Accelerating Time-to-experiment for Remote RI Coupling

The developments of JRA2.2.5 served as the basis for the development of services within the JRA3. The summary of these developments is presented in the next subsection.

3.3 JRA3 Services

JRA3 involves the development of a set of services that facilitate the interconnection of geographically separated RIs. The services under development are summarized below:

3.3.1 Virtual Overlay Network

Geographically Distributed Simulation (GDS) or experiment requires the establishment of a communication link between the two (or more) RIs involved. Direct communication between different RIs can be restricted due to security concerns. To address this concern, a transparent overlay network is established between the RIs to be interconnected. This overlay network employs Virtual Private Network (VPN) solutions to create a mesh of peer-to-peer connections between all RIs. The implementation of the virtual overlay network has been tested within the scope of JRA2, establishing a peer-peer connection between up to three RIs.

3.3.2 Provisioning and Orchestration

To facilitate the equipment within a RI to communicate with equipment within other RIs, a gateway that implements the virtual overlay network is required. This is enabled through a mobile unit – a mobile computing device acting as a gateway between a RI equipment and other remote RIs. Provisioning refers to the automatic setup and maintenance of these units, removing the human from the loop, saving time, and effort. In a similar manner, orchestration refers to the management of GDS setups and sequence of experiments through scripts.

3.3.3 Data Exchange

Each RI with the combination of equipment, data formats, communications protocols and practices is unique. A GDS would typically involve the exchange of data between the interconnected RIs. To facilitate the seamless exchange of data, a service that enables interfacing multiple data formats and protocols is integrated. This service further allows the capability to control the rate of data transmission between the RIs.

3.3.4 Network Monitoring

The geographical distances between the RIs to be interconnected introduce large latencies that can impact the accuracy and stability of the GDS. To understand the impact of the latencies and to adopt mitigating measures to alleviate their deteriorating impact, a measurement of these latencies is required. In addition, understanding the detailed status of the communication network (such as the bandwidth, packet loss, throughput, etc.) can allow for the development of advanced techniques to mitigate the impact of the latencies. For this purpose, a network monitoring service is under development that utilizes the well-established perfSonar¹ tool suite adapted for use in Kubernetes cluster.

¹<https://www.perfsonar.net/>

3.3.5 Network Emulation

Many smart grid controls rely upon communications, particularly distributed and centralized control schemes. Incorporation of realistic communication characteristics in experimental evaluations is desirable rather than the use of static delays. This service offers the RIs to incorporate realistic emulation of real-world network characteristics when undertaking single RI or GDS. It further allows the users to configure one or more traffic profiles to impair network traffic between the interconnected RIs.

3.3.6 Time-Synchronization

This service is developed to allow for a common time base for appropriate temporal alignment of experimental results obtained through the interconnection of multiple RIs. Time synchronization is provided through Global Positioning System (GPS), Network Time Protocol (NTP), or the Precision Time Protocol (PTP).

4 Project Demonstrations

This section presents a brief summary of the five chosen demonstrations within the ERIGrid 2.0 project, highlighting the key advancement brought forward with respect to the objective of extending the capabilities of RIs.

4.1 Demonstration 1: Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL

Description: Research institutes but also the industry, have started undertaking Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL) and PHIL experiments to accelerate the rigorous validation of new control schemes in smart grids and study the dynamic behavior of hardware devices under conditions close to real. With this method, real pieces of hardware are tested in real-time closed-loop experiments to observe the interactions with the energy system to be connected.

HIL enables the testing of the behavior of the Hardware under Test (HUT) in a safe manner, that is, in a controlled laboratory environment, taking into account at the same time the imperfections that exist in real world, like delays, noise, etc., which are usually neglected in pure simulation testing. Thus, HIL acts as an intermediate step that bridges the gap between pure simulation and experiments on the field. An open research topic is how to improve the stability of a PHIL setups without reducing their accuracy, in terms of the power exchange between the two systems. In literature (Ren, Steurer, & Baldwin, 2008), several Interface Algorithm (IA)s have been proposed to deal with this issue, but some of them concern methods of high complexity with limited applicability.

Within the ERIGrid 2.0 project, proven and easy to implement existing methods for the enhancement of stability and accuracy of PHIL setups were considered. Indicatively, the feedback current filtering, shifting impedance and time delay compensation methods. Based on those, a new IA was developed utilizing their properties and overcoming some of the limitations they present. In this demonstration, the enhanced accuracy and stability of PHIL setups will be demonstrated in simple and complex setups, as well as in smart grid applications.

Link to JRAs: Demonstration 1 plans to utilize the Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation (VSIDC) IA that improves the stability and accuracy of PHIL experiments, which was developed in the frame of JRA2. Apart from VSIDC, other widely used IAs might be utilized as well. Additionally, the framework developed in JRA2 for the analysis of sensitivity properties and dynamics of HIL will be implemented.

Advancement: Adding a Low-Pass Filter (LPF) in the feedback current is one of the simplest and straightforward methods to improve PHIL stability, but if no other complementary actions take place, it can highly compromise the accuracy. Shifting impedance suggests transferring part of the impedance from the simulated side to the hardware side, which increases the stability of the overall setup and allows the use of a higher cut-off frequency feedback filter, substantially reducing the occurred inaccuracy.

Time delay compensation compensates for the phase shift introduced from the different components of the simulated side, leading to increased accuracy of the PHIL experiments. Studying the aforementioned enhancing methods, a new one, the Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation was developed. Based on this, the stability and accuracy properties of Shifting Impedance and Delay Compensation were utilized, while additionally, a way of introducing virtually the impedance in the controller of the amplifier was suggested. The major advantage of

VSIDC is that improves accuracy during transients and eliminates the need of using hardware impedance. Finally, the sensitivity framework to be applied will enable the precise estimation of the PHIL experiments' stability properties prior to the testing.

Table 1: Summary of Demonstration 1.

Demonstration 1: Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL	
Partners	National Technical University of Athens (ICCS) University of Strathclyde (UoS) Commissariat A L Energie Atomique Et Aux Energies Alternatives (CEA) Fundacion TECNALIA Research & Innovation (TEC)
Laboratories	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS) Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UoS)
Experiment Type	Single RI Hardware-in-the-Loop
JRA2 Development	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation, and Sensitivity Framework
JRA1 Test Case	Complying with the Fault-Ride-Through (FRT) requirements in inverter-based droop-controlled microgrids
JRA3 Services	n/a

In Figure 2, the timeline of Demonstration 1 implementation is presented. Initially, the VSIDC interface algorithm will be validated and demonstrated in a PHIL setup with passive HUT, which is a passive load bank. As a next step, the method will be demonstrated in a PHIL setup with an active hardware component, like a Photovoltaic (PV) inverter.

Ultimately, advanced control schemes and scenarios in inverter-based microgrids will be tested and demonstrated, highlighting the importance of conducting accurate PHIL experiments to observe more precisely the behaviour of such systems.

Figure 2: Timeline for Demonstration 1.

Table 2: Tasks for Demonstration 1.

Demonstration 1: Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL	
Task 1	Validation of Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation (VSIDC) with passive HUT
Task 2	Validation of Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation (VSIDC) with active HUT
Task 3	PHIL setup for testing ancillary services provided by Distributed Energy Resources (DERs)

4.2 Demonstration 2: Time Delay Compensation

Description: Time delay is an inherent characteristic of any closed-loop PHIL setup affecting both its accuracy and stability. High fidelity PHIL set-ups are conventionally realised through the compensation of time delay, which is variable yet deterministic for such setups. The renewed challenge is presented through the emergence of GDSs where two or more Digital Real-Time Simulator (DRTS) are interconnected over the Internet through a similar interface algorithm as utilised in PHIL setups. The indeterministic nature of the exchange of data through the Internet presents a challenge for the determination of the time delay and its consequent compensation to realise high-fidelity simulations.

Link to JRAs: Demonstration 2 is based on the approaches developed in JRA2 and will be carried out by employing the tools developed in JRA2. The key aspects of this demonstration are the in-depth assessments of the time delay compensation developed in JRA2 and the performance evaluation of the GPS based time delay compensation method regarding its applicability and capability for providing delay compensation to the GDRTS setup.

Advancement: While GPS time-stamped signals exchange presents a viable approach to the development of an accurate time-delay compensation method, two additional time delay compensation methods have been realized within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. The objective of this test case is to characterize the performance of the two methods against the GPS based time delay compensation. The advancement of these methods will be demonstrated through the experiment.

Table 3: Summary of Demonstration 2.

Demonstration 2: Time Delay Compensation	
Partners	University of Strathclyde (UoS) RWTH Aachen University (RWTH) National Technical University of Athens (ICCS)
Laboratories	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UoS) RTlab (RWTH)
Experiment Type	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulations
JRA2 Development	Time Delay Compensation for High Fidelity Validations
JRA1 Test Case	Synthetic Inertia and Fast Frequency Response by Converter based Resources
JRA3 Services	Data Exchange Network Monitoring

Figure 3: Timeline for Demonstration 2.

Table 4: Tasks for Demonstration 2.

Demonstration 2: Time Delay Compensation	
Task 1	Network Monitoring Deployment
Task 2	Gathering Data for Network Monitoring
Task 3	Development of Probabilistic and Artificial Intelligence (AI) based Approaches
Task 4	Experiment between UoS and RWTH

4.3 Demonstration 3: Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Testing

Description: This demonstration introduces tools to accelerate the setup and the coordination of highly distributed experiments. As a use case, an optimal Coordinated Voltage Control (CVC) operating as a distribution management system is chosen. The algorithm manages all the devices of the network that are capable of regulating the voltage either directly (through On-Load Tap Changer (OLTC)s) or through the injection of active/reactive power, such as Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) and PV inverters.

The management is based on the solution of an optimisation problem, which minimises a pre-defined objective function, subject to linear and non-linear constraints. In order to showcase the scalability of the developed tools, almost half of the project members, around ten labs, are planned to participate in the demonstration by either providing real-time simulation, PHIL, or CHIL resources.

Link to JRAs: Demonstration 3 plans to utilise the tools developed in JRA2 & JRA3 to a high degree. It will be built upon the ERIGrid 2.0 middle-ware introduced in JRA3. The foundation of the infrastructure will be interconnected by a set of mobile units, which are jointly managed as a Research Infrastructure as Code (RIasC) cluster. The RIasC tooling developed in JRA2 & JRA3 will provide functions to establish transparent communication between the mobile units via an overlay network. The time-synchronisation service will establish a common time reference required for the distributed collection of simulation results.

The network monitoring and emulation services are planned to be used for emulating contingencies in the communication network. Last but not least, a rapid and repeatable setup of the experiment shall be demonstrated by the automated provisioning and deployment tools of RIasC, which are enabled by the Kubernetes cloud technology².

Advancement: Traditionally, the setup of distributed experiments required a considerable amount of manual labour for the configuration of involved lab equipment. This demonstration attempts to showcase a new methodology in which these manual steps are automated based on a common experiment description. This methodology is inspired by the latest trends in the cloud computing field, also known as Infrastructure as Code. Here, this paradigm has been extended and is referred to as RIasC.

²<https://riasc.eu>

Table 5: Summary of Demonstration 3.

Demonstration 3: Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for remote RI testing	
Partners	RWTH Aachen University (RWTH) Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES) Fundacion TECNALIA Research & Innovation (TEC) University of Strathclyde (UoS) SINTEF Energi AS (SINTEF) Danmarks Tekniske Universtet (DTU) Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy (VTT) Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives (CEA) Ormazabal Corporate Technology, A.I.E. (OCT)
Laboratories	RTlab (RWTH) Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS) PV & DG-Lab (CRES) Smart Grid Technologies Lab (TEC) Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UoS) National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF) SYSLAB (DTU) IntelligentEnergy testbed (VTT) Smart Grids Laboratory (CEA) UDEX Demonstration & Experimentation Unit (OCT)
Experiment Type	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulations
JRA2 Development	JRA2.2.5 - Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for remote-RI interconnection
JRA1 Test Case	TC15 - Smart Grid Control Algorithm – Optimal Centralized Coordinated Voltage Ctrl
JRA3 Services	Data Exchange Network Monitoring Network Emulation Time-synchronization Virtual Overlay Network Provisioning and orchestration via RlasC cluster

Figure 4: Timeline for Demonstration 3.

Table 6: Tasks for Demonstration 3.

Demonstration 3: Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for remote RI testing	
Task 1	Validation of Model, HIL Interfaces and CVC Controller
Task 2	RI Substitution & Point of Common Coupling (PCC) Swap
Task 3	Communication Network Emulation
Task 4	Repeatability and Time-to-first-Simulation

4.4 Demonstration 4: Multi-Energy District Flexibility

Description: Flexibility provision by local energy systems has been identified as one of the viable solutions to the challenges offered by the large diffusion of non-programmable renewable energy sources. Based on this background, this demonstration aims to investigate the technical feasibility of power-to-heat service provision in a local multi-energy district and its impact on both the electric and thermal networks.

In particular, the flexibility requested by the Distribution System Operator (DSO) can be provided by a combination of electric and thermal storage systems as well as demand response from flexible controllable loads, such as heat pumps, thermal loads, electric boilers, etc. In this context, the heating system can provide services to the electrical system, e.g., (a) congestion management – electrical import and export limitation and (b) balancing power provision.

Link to JRAs: Demonstration 4 will use the tools developed by JRA2 and JRA3. In particular, the multi-energy district will be emulated by integrating equipment in multiple RIs. To allow this integration data will be exchanged among the RIs using the tool developed in JRA2. Data will be managed using the services provided by JRA3.

Advancement: Multi-energy districts are complex systems involving multiple domains and resources. Since it is difficult to replicate such systems in a unique laboratory, a simulation, co-simulation or HIL approach is usually applied for testing. This demonstration allows performing a pure hardware test coupling resources in different research infrastructures, creating an Extended RI with greater capability than every single laboratory integrated.

Table 7: Summary of Demonstration 4.

Demonstration 4: Multi-Energy District Flexibility	
Partners	Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (RSE) Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES) Danmarks Tekniske Universtet (DTU) Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD) SINTEF Energi AS (SINTEF)
Laboratories	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE) PV & DG Lab (CRES) Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TUD) National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF) SYSLAB (DTU)
Experiment Type	Geographically Distributed Power and Heat in the loop
JRA2 Development	Accelerating time-to-experiment for remote RI coupling
JRA1 Test Case	TC11 – Characterization of power-to-heat service availability and its network impact
JRA3 Services	Data Exchange, Network Monitoring, Time-synchronization

Figure 5: Timeline for Demonstration 4.

Table 8: Tasks for Demonstration 4.

Demonstration 4: Multi-Energy District Flexibility	
Task 1	Experimental Test Case and extended research infrastructure validation
Task 2	Congestion management
Task 3	Active power control at the electric network PCC.
Task 4	Balancing power provision

4.5 Demonstration 5: AC & ICT Co-Simulation

Description: Smart grids have become a complex system of systems characterized by mutual interactions and interdependency between the power system and the ICT systems. To evaluate the system-level integration and validation of such a system, proper attention should be focused on the design of simulation tools which can simulate the two systems holistically. So far, there are no established cyber-physical approaches or software tools for designing, analyzing, and validating smart grid systems sufficiently in such a manner. ERIGrid 2.0 addresses

this gap by developing a co-simulation-based approach. The purpose of this demonstration (Demonstration 5) is to test and characterize the co-simulation tool used for interfacing AC and ICT systems.

Link to JRAs: Demonstration 5 plans to utilize a software co-simulation framework for interfacing AC and ICT simulators which have been developed in JRA2.1. The framework uses mosaik 3.0 as a co-simulation master and interfaces all simulators (ICT, AC and controller) via the newly released third revision (*FMI for Model Exchange, Co-Simulation, and Scheduled Execution*, 2022) of the FMI standard. Both mosaik 3.0 and FMI 3.0 now include dedicated support for event-based co-simulation which were missing in previous versions.

Advancement: The co-simulation framework developed in ERIGrid 2.0 presents a viable approach for studying and validating complex smart grid systems. This demonstration use case aims to characterize the performance of the simulation approach developed in JRA2 by comparing the dynamics of the simulated system to the dynamics of a comparable physical (laboratory) setup. This is the first step towards a validation test, exploring the range of achievable performance. The data collected would allow a reference scale (pass/fail) to be developed at a later time.

Table 9: Summary of Demonstration 5.

Demonstration 5: AC & ICT Co-Simulation	
Partners	SINTEF Energi AS (SINTEF) Denmark Technical University (DTU)
Laboratories	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF) SYSLAB (DTU)
Experiment Type	Single RI experiment
JRA2 Development	JRA2.1 AC and ICT co-simulation framework
JRA1 Test Case	TC 17 - Fault tolerance/ recovery of a multi-aggregator dispatch mechanism
JRA3 Services	n/a

Figure 6: Timeline for Demonstration 5.

Table 10: Tasks for Demonstration 5.

Demonstration 5: AC & ICT Co-Simulation	
Task 1	Model development / control system implementation
Task 2	Co-simulation test/experiment
Task 3	Physical test/experiment

5 KPIs for Enhanced Capabilities of Extended RIs

In the context of JRA4.1 different KPIs have been developed. These KPIs will be used to evaluate the performance of the ERIGrid 2.0 extended RIs and offer insights into the applicability of the RIs for addressing pertinent research questions the community faces.

The KPIs for the five different demo cases of JRA4 are based on a list of questions/questionnaire, which have to be answered/filled in by researchers of the participating RIs during preparation, conduction or assessment of the experiments that are part of the demonstrations. The results will be evaluated in JRA4.4

In the following, a few general KPIs questions which are relevant to all five demonstration cases are presented. These general questions are mainly focusing on management aspects and they might be interesting for non-technical stakeholders, industrial clients or interested academic users. Then, the subsequent sections present technical questions that are relevant for each specific demonstration.

5.1 General Questions

Eleven general questions will assess the advancement of the method adopted compared to the state of the art from different points of view.

1. Which problem is addressed in Demonstration No. x?
2. What is the motivation for solving this problem?
3. What is the existing state of the art for solving this problem?
4. What are the added values of Demonstration No. x compared to the state of the art in terms of
 - Accuracy?
 - Temporal Resolution?
 - Scalability?
 - Scientific Expertise of the involved RIs?
 - Services extensions for the involved RI/partners?
5. Quantify the time for conduction of the experiments of Demonstration No. x (Days of Lab usage)
6. Quantify the time for preparation of the experiments of Demonstration No. x (Time to experiment in days)
7. How large are the changes/improvements of the participating RIs compared to the situation before?
Use the scale with following five levels (5=huge; 4=large; 3=moderate; 2=little; 1=no).
8. Quantify the cost-savings of Demonstration No. x compared to other solutions
Use the scale with following five levels (5=huge; 4=large; 3=moderate; 2=little; 1=no).
9. What is the status (i.e., Technology Readiness Level (TRL)) of the experiment implementation compared to the state of the art?

10. How important is Demonstration No x to the strategic targets of the participating RIs? (Give examples)
Use the scale with the following five levels (5=huge; 4=large; 3=moderate; 2=little; 1=no).
11. How important is Demonstration No. x to the lab staff professional development of the participating RIs? (Give examples)
Use the scale with following five levels (5=huge; 4=large; 3=moderate; 2=little; 1=no).

5.2 Questions Specific to Demonstration 1

The following questions are relevant for Demonstration 1.

1. Quantify the improvement of the stability region for PHIL experiments with VSIDC compared to other interface algorithms based on stability and sensitivity analysis.
2. Quantify the improvement of accuracy for PHIL experiments with VSIDC compared to other interface algorithms.
3. How big are the maximum errors in steady state active and reactive power exchange at the PCC with VSIDC compared to theoretical results? (TS D1.1)
4. How big are the maximum errors during transient events regarding active and reactive power exchange at the PCC with VSIDC compared to theoretical results? (TS D1.2)

5.3 Questions Specific to Demonstration 2

The following questions are relevant for Demonstration 2.

1. Quantify the improvement of accuracy (especially for geographically distributed) HIL experiments for the following time delay compensation methods compared to state-of-the-art:
 - GPS based time delay compensation
 - Probabilistic time delay compensation
 - Data-driven time delay compensation
2. Quantify the improvement of stability (especially for geographically distributed) HIL experiments for the following time delay compensation methods compared to state-of-the-art:
 - GPS based time delay compensation
 - Probabilistic time delay compensation
 - Data-driven time delay compensation
3. How big are the maximum errors in steady state active and reactive power exchange at the PCC for the different time delay compensation methods? (TS D2.1)
4. How big are the maximum errors in active and reactive power exchange and system frequency at the PCC for the different time delay compensation methods in smart grid applications? (TS D2.2)

5.4 Questions Specific to Demonstration 3

The following questions are relevant for Demonstration 3.

1. Quantify the initial and the repeated setup time for conduction of the experiments in the different RIs.
2. How large are the improvements regarding the manual configuration efforts for the conduction of the experiments in the different RIs?
Use the scale with following five levels (5=huge; 4=large; 3=moderate; 2=little; 1=no).
3. How large are the time savings for re-configuration (parameter change) of software controllers in the different RIs?
4. How many persons (Information Technology (IT), Administrative, Technical, Supervisory) are necessary for setting up the experiments in the different RIs? Quantify the reductions.

5.5 Questions Specific to Demonstration 4

The following questions are relevant for Demonstration 4.

1. Quantify the improvements in flexibility of sector coupling of thermal and electrical energy in the participating RIs.
Use the scale with following five levels (5=huge; 4=large; 3=moderate; 2=little; 1=no).
2. Quantify the violations of electrical (energy/power) limits in the participating RIs.
Use for quantification either suitable units [kWh, kW] or %.
3. Quantify the deviations of the electrical (energy/power) exchange setpoints at the PCC.
Use for quantification either suitable units [kWh, kW] or %.
4. How big are the deviations of thermal setpoints (energy, temperatures) in the participating RIs?
Use for quantification either suitable units [kWh, °K] or %.
5. Quantify the reduction of thermal and electrical power losses in the participating RIs.
Use for quantification either suitable units [kW] or %.
6. What is the additional electrical and thermal capacity used in the experiment compared to the single RI experiment?
Use for quantification either suitable units [kW] or %.
7. What is the additional electrical and thermal capacity emulated in the experiment compared to the single RI experiment?
Use for quantification either suitable units [kW] or %.
8. What is the additional electrical and thermal capacity simulated in the experiment compared to the single RI experiment?
Use for quantification either suitable units [kW] or %.

5.6 Questions Specific to Demonstration 5

The following questions are relevant for Demonstration 5.

1. Quantify the accuracy of the co-simulation compared to the comparable laboratory setup. Use for quantification the unit %.
2. How large are the deviations of service delivered from service requested (TCR1) for the following variables?
 - Overall integral error [kWh]
 - Maximum overall service deviation [kW]
 - Mean overall service deviation [kW]
 - Maximum individual integral error [kWh]
 - Maximum individual service deviation [kW]

Use for quantification either suitable units [kWh, kW] or %.

3. How large are the deviations of time to restore steady-state operation after a failure event in the communication domain (TCR2) for the following variables?
 - Time from occurrence to detection of communication failure [ms].
 - Time from detection of communication failure to end of distribution of new setpoints to unit controllers [ms].
 - Time from reception of new setpoints at unit controllers to (physical) service restoration [ms].

Use for quantification either the unit [ms] or %.

4. How large are the deviations of time to restore steady-state operation after a failure event in the electrical domain (TCR3) for the following variables?
5. Time from occurrence to detection of electrical equipment failure [ms].
6. Time from detection of electrical equipment failure to end of the distribution of new setpoints to unit controllers [ms].
7. Time from reception of new setpoints at unit controllers to (physical) service restoration [ms] Use for quantification either the unit [ms] or %.

6 Conclusions

The objective of JRA4.1 is to document a shortlisted set of advanced methods and services taken forward as demonstrations within the scope of JRA4.3.

This work presents the methodology that has been adopted to downselect a set of advanced methods and services for demonstration within the ERIGrid 2.0 project. The methodology ensured the planned demonstrations built upon the work already undertaken as part of other WPs (i.e., NA4, JRA1, JRA2, and JRA3). The test cases developed as part of NA4 have provided the smart grid context within which the advanced methods of JRA2 can be demonstrated, while JRA1 developed benchmark systems have been chosen for utilization (with modifications where necessary) within the demonstrations. Furthermore, the development of the demonstrations has further refined and informed about the requirements of the services currently under development in JRA3. There were five demonstrations finalized to be taken forward:

- Demonstration 1: Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL
- Demonstration 2: Time Delay Compensation
- Demonstration 3: Accelerated Time to Experiments for Remote RI Testing
- Demonstration 4: Multi-Energy District Flexibility
- Demonstration 5: AC & ICT Co-Simulation

Each of the demonstrations has been documented in detail utilizing the HTD template, comprising the test case narrative, the test specification and the experiment specifications. The detailed plan for the implementation of the demonstration, including the partners and RIs involved, has been identified. A tentative timeline for the implementation of the demonstrations has been given, including the incorporation of the identified services of JRA3 (i.e., JRA4.2) and subsequent experiments between the RIs. In addition, the KPIs for the assessment of the extended capabilities of the RIs have been defined in the form of a questionnaire. It is intended that the evaluation will be undertaken as part of JRA4.4, upon successful completion of the demonstrations in JRA4.3.

The direct next steps involve the incorporation of the chosen advanced methods and identified services within the respective RIs. These activities will continue within JRA4.2.

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Appendix 1: Demonstration 1 HTD

Test Description

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Version: 0.1

Project: ERIGrid 2.0

Name of the Test Case	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation & Sensitivity Framework
Narrative	<p>An advanced method for improving stability and accuracy of PHIL experiments is considered. It was developed based on existing proven ones, namely the shifting impedance and the time delay compensation, aiming to combine and take advantage of their properties. At the same time, the method expanded to overcome some limitations, like the need for availability of actual hardware impedance. This method while increasing stability of the PHIL setup, also improves the accuracy.</p> <p>This TC aims to verify and validate the properties of VSIDC interface algorithm in simple and more complex scenarios. Moreover, the sensitivity framework will be employed to precisely estimate the PHIL system properties prior to experimental testing.</p>
Function(s) under Investigation (Ful) the referenced specification of a function realized (operationalized) by the object under investigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applicability of VSIDC interface algorithm • Accuracy and stability assessment of VSIDC
Object under Investigation (Oul) the component(s) (1..n) that are to be qualified by the test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VSIDC interface algorithm • The tested HUT
Domain under Investigation (Dul) the relevant domains or sub-domains of test parameters and connectivity	Electrical Domain
Purpose of Investigation (Pol) The test purpose in terms of Characterization, Verification, or Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characterization and validation of the System under Test (SuT) • Verification and validation of the Oul • Verification and validation of the Ful
System under Test (SuT) Systems, subsystems, components included in the test case or test setup	PHIL setup with passive or active load.

<p>Functions under Test (FuT) Functions relevant to the operation of the system under test, including FuT and relevant interactions btw. Oul and SuT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applicability of VSIDC interface algorithm • Accuracy and stability assessment of VSIDC
<p>Test Criteria (TCR) Formulation of criteria for each PoI based on properties of SuT; encompasses properties of test signals and output measures.</p>	<p>Evaluation of the stability and accuracy of the setups realized through the incorporation of the VSIDC</p>
<p>Target Metrics (TM) Measures required to quantify identified test criteria</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current and voltage measurements • Error in active and reactive power exchange at point of common coupling. • Time delay • Sensitivity functions
<p>Variability Attributes (VA) controllable or uncontrollable factors and the required variability; ref. to PoI</p>	<p>Variability factors include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Varying cut-off frequency of feedback filter • Varying ratio of software and hardware impedance
<p>Quality Attributes (QA) threshold levels for test result quality as well as the definition of a decision rule such as pass/fail criteria</p>	<p>Proper stability margins and accuracy metrics (e.g. Phw=Psw, etc)</p>

Test Specification TS D1.1

<p>Reference to Test Case</p>	<p>TC D1</p>
<p>Title of Test</p>	<p>Validation of Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation (VSIDC)</p>
<p>Test Rationale</p>	<p>This test aims to validate the developed VSIDC method in a PHIL setup with passive/active HUT.</p>
<p>Specific Test System (graphical)</p>	<p>Simple voltage divider circuit.</p> <p>The diagram illustrates a voltage divider circuit. On the left, a green box labeled 'DRTS' contains an 'Equivalent Thevenin of simulated power network' with a voltage source V_D and current I_D. It is connected to an 'Interface Algorithm' block. This block is further connected to another 'Interface Algorithm & Power Amplifier' block, which is connected to a 'HUT' (Passive load bank/ Inverter filter) represented by a blue box. The HUT contains an equivalent circuit with resistors R_2 and X_2. The output voltage is V_A and the current is I_A.</p>

Target measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stability assessment • Active power and reactive power at the point of common coupling and accuracy assessment • Sensitivity functions • Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) and Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) measurements
Input and output parameters	<p>Input:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Load/Hardware device • Grid condition <p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voltage, current and power measurements, during steady and transient states
Test Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The simulation at DRTS starts first • The voltage is applied to the amplifier and measured • The voltage of the amplifier is output to the HUT and current and voltage measurements are taken • Finally, the loop closes, and the accuracy of the system is estimated
Initial system state	The system is initialised and synchronized at nominal values of voltage (230 V) and frequency (50 Hz).
Evolution of system state and test signals	Use of different sets of Z_s , Z_h and LPF (feedback filters) to compare experimental results with theoretical stability margins.
Other parameters	n/a
Temporal resolution	16 kHz, 50 μ s.
Source of uncertainty	Amplifier's response (delay, amplification), sensors imperfections, HUT's behavior in case of active component, etc.
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Suspension – Instability Stopping: Successful evolution of system states and recording of target measures.

Test Specification TS D1.2

Reference to Test Case	TC D1
Title of Test	PHIL setup for testing the compliance with FRT requirements and other ancillary services provided by DERs

<p>Test Rationale</p>	<p>A microgrid application is considered, in which DERs feed the load and achieve power sharing. At the same time, the voltage and frequency of the microgrid are regulated close to their nominal values (droop control operation). Furthermore, when a fault occurs, the inverters inject power according to international standards to provide grid support. Advanced interface algorithms, like delay compensation and VSIDC which was developed in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0, will be utilized to make the PHIL setup stable and to provide more accurate results of testing.</p>
<p>Specific Test System (graphical)</p>	
<p>Target measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inverter power injection, load voltage and frequency, inverter currents • Active power and reactive power at the point of common coupling and accuracy assessment • Stability assessment • Sensitivity functions • SNR and THD measurements
<p>Input and output parameters</p>	<p>Input:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Load • Inverter power injection set-points • Grid condition <p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voltage, current and power measurements, during steady and transient states

Test Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operate a set of inverters in parallel • Perform a network fault when the microgrid operates either in islanded (non-interconnected) mode or in grid-connected mode • Save the experimental results
Initial system state	The system is initialised and synchronized at nominal values of voltage (230 V) and frequency (50 Hz).
Evolution of system state and test signals	The system goes from normal operation (operation close to nominal voltage and frequency) to operation under fault, to test the inverter behavior
Other parameters	n/a
Temporal resolution	16 kHz (in case a switched-type amplifier is used), 50 μ s.
Source of uncertainty	Hardware inverter's response, amplifier's response (delay, amplification), sensors imperfections, etc.
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Suspension: Abnormal current, Instability Stopping: Successful evolution of system states and recording of target measures.

Experiment Specification ES D1.1

Reference to Test Specification	TS D2.1
Title of Experiment	Validation of VSIDC method in PHIL setup with passive load
Research Infrastructure	EESL (ICCS-NTUA) and DPSL (Strathclyde)
Experiment Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing the interface topology in the real-time simulator, and the proposed interface algorithm • Designing of the appropriate software protection • Hardware interfaces
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) • Interfacing I/O cards • PC for RSCAD (UI of RTDS) • Switching Amplifier (Triphase) • Hardware passive load • Metering devices
Experimental Design and Justification	In RSCAD the simulated part will be designed based on known interface topologies (Voltage-Type Ideal Transformer Model (V-ITM), etc). Then the VSIDC will be designed in the controller of the power amplifier and finally, the HUT will be interfaced to RTDS through the amplifier.

Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 μs time step • precision of the used ammeter • Delay introduced for the D/A and A/D conversions • Delay introduced and non-ideal output response of the amplifier
Storage of experiment data	RTDS – Various formats (excel, dat, cfg, etc).

Experiment Specification ES D1.2

Reference to Test Specification	TS D1.1
Title of Experiment	PHIL for analysing inverter's response in real condition
Research Infrastructure	DPSL (Strathclyde) or EESL (ICCS-NTUA)
Experiment Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microgrid design in RSCAD • Designing of the appropriate software protection • Hardware interfaces
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) • Interfacing I/O cards • PC for RSCAD (UI of RTDS) • Switching Amplifier (Triphase) • Hardware solar inverter • Metering devices
Experimental Design and Justification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In RSCAD an inverter-based microgrid will be designed. The inverters will be simulated as controlled voltage sources to facilitate testing under various grid conditions. • FRT curve according to Grid Codes, will be used. • A hardware inverter will be connected to RTDS to perform PHIL experiments and validate the performance under real conditions.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 μs time step • precision of the used ammeter • Delay introduced for the D/A and A/D conversions • Delay introduced and non-ideal output response of the amplifier
Storage of experiment data	RSCAD – Various formats (excel, dat, cfg, etc).

Appendix 2: Demonstration 2 HTD

Test Description

Authors: M. Syed (UoS), Z. Feng (UoS), S. Vogel (RWTH), A. Kontou (ICCS), A. Paspatis (ICCS), T.The Hoang (CEA)

Version: 0.1

Project: ERIGrid 2.0

Name of the Test Case	Time Delay Compensation
Narrative	<p>Time delay is an inherent characteristic of any closed-loop power hardware in the loop (PHIL) setup affecting both accuracy and stability of the setup. High fidelity PHIL set-ups are conventionally realised through the compensation of time delay, that is variable yet deterministic for such setups. The renewed challenge is presented through the emergence of geographically distributed simulations where two or more digital real-time simulators (DRTS) are interconnected over the Internet through a similar interface algorithm as utilised in PHIL setups. The indeterministic nature of the exchange of data through the Internet presents a challenge for the determination of the time delay and its consequent compensation to realise high fidelity simulations.</p> <p>While GPS time-stamped signals exchange presents a viable approach to development of accurate time-delay compensation method, two* additional time delay compensation methods have been realized within the ERIGRID 2.0 project. The objective of this test case is to characterize the performance of the two methods against the GPS based time delay compensation.</p>
Function(s) under Investigation (Ful) the referenced specification of a function realized (operationalized) by the object under investigation	The time delay compensation methods developed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GPS based time delay compensation. • Probabilistic time delay compensation. • Data-driven time delay compensation.
Object under Investigation (Oul) the component(s) (1..n) that are to be qualified by the test	The two DRTS at the two research infrastructures.
Domain under Investigation (Dul) the relevant domains or sub-domains of test parameters and connectivity	Electrical Domain ICT Domain
Purpose of Investigation (Pol) The test purpose in terms of Characterization, Verification, or Validation	Pol 1: To validate the developed time delay compensation methods Pol 2: To characterize the accuracy of the setups realized through the integration of the three* time delay compensation methods.
System under Test (SuT) Systems, subsystems, components included in the test case or test setup	Voltage divider circuit split for simulation across the two DRTS.

<p>Functions under Test (FuT) Functions relevant to the operation of the system under test, including FuL and relevant interactions btw. Oul and SuT</p>	<p>For all compensation methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interface signals reconstruction (the function depends on the transformation chosen) <p>For GPS based time delay compensation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GPS time-stamp signal
<p>Test criteria (TCR) Formulation of criteria for each PoL based on properties of SuT; encompasses properties of test signals and output measures.</p>	<p>Evaluation of accuracy of the setups realized through the incorporation of the time-delay compensation methods</p>
<p>Target Metrics (TM) Measures required to quantify each identified test criteria</p>	<p>The measure required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time delay • Error in active and reactive power exchange at point of common coupling.
<p>Variability Attributes (VA) controllable or uncontrollable factors and the required variability; ref. to PoL</p>	<p>Variability factors include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time of day of experiment • Size of data packet
<p>Quality Attributes (QA) threshold levels for test result quality as well as the definition of a decision rule such as pass/fail criteria</p>	<p>Successful (stable) realization of the voltage divider circuit synchronization over the two DRTS with incorporation of the time-delay compensation methods.</p>

Test Specification TS D2.1

<p>Reference to Test Case</p>	<p>TC D2</p>
<p>Title of Test</p>	<p>Validation of Time Delay Compensation</p>
<p>Test Rationale</p>	<p>This test aims to validate the developed time delay compensation methods.</p>
<p>Specific Test System (graphical)</p>	<p>A voltage divider circuit split for simulation in DRTS at two research infrastructures.</p>
<p>Target measures</p>	<p>Active power and reactive power at the point of common coupling.</p>
<p>Input and output parameters</p>	<p>n/a</p>

Test Design	The simulation at either end is started and the two systems synchronized without time delay compensation. Voltage and frequency step up and down are emulated to evaluate the accuracy of the time delay compensation method during dynamics. Target metrics are recorded for each event. The above events are repeated when time delay compensation method is turned on.
Initial system state	The system is initialized and synchronized at nominal values of voltage (230 V) and frequency (50 Hz).
Evolution of system state and test signals	A positive 23 V (0.1 pu) step is initiated, followed by a negative 23 V step to bring the system back to nominal values. A negative 23 V step is initiated followed by a positive step to bring the voltage back to nominal values. The frequency is changed from 50 Hz to 51 Hz and is then brought back to nominal value of 50 Hz. The frequency is changed from 50 Hz to 49 Hz and is then brought back to 50 Hz
Other parameters	All other parameters are kept constant.
Temporal resolution	20 kHz, 50 us.
Source of uncertainty	Time of Day.
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Suspension –Instability Stopping: Successful evolution of system states and recording of target measures.

Test Specification TS D2.2

Reference to Test Case	TC D2
Title of Test	Characterization of Time Delay Compensation Methods in Smart Grid Application
Test Rationale	This test aims to characterize the performance of the developed time delay compensation methods against the time delay compensation method using GPS. The test is performed within the context of a smart grid application, i.e., inertia provision, to demonstrate the effectiveness of the approaches.
Specific Test System (graphical)	The reduced model of the Great Britain (GB) power system is utilized. The system is split for simulation in two research infrastructures. Implementation of inertial control:
Target measures	Active power and reactive power at the point of common coupling and the frequency of the system.
Input and output parameters:	

Test Design	The simulation at either end is started and the two systems synchronized without time delay compensation. Voltage and frequency step up and down are emulated to evaluate the accuracy of the time delay compensation method during dynamics. Target metrics are recorded for each event. The above events are repeated when time delay compensation method is turned on.
Initial system state	The system is initialized and synchronized at nominal values of voltage (230 V) and frequency (50 Hz).
Evolution of system state and test signals	To initiate a frequency event, a 1 GW load is added on to the network to emulate a generator loss.
Other parameters	All other parameters are kept constant.
Temporal resolution	20 kHz
Source of uncertainty	Time of Day Size of data packet
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Suspension –Instability Stopping: Successful evolution of system states and recording of target measures.

Experiment Specification ES D2.1

Reference to Test Specification	TS D2.1
Title of Experiment	Validation of Time Delay Compensation
Research Infrastructure	DPSSL (Strathclyde) and RWTH Aachen?
Experiment Realisation	The subsystem with voltage source and controlled current source is simulated in the DRTS at DPSSL and the subsystem with load and controlled voltage source is simulated at RWTH Aachen. The GT-NET cards communicate over the internet (reference case) establishing the performance of the GPS based time delay compensation method.
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DRTS with GT-Sync and GT-NET (x2) cards at each RI • DRTS Host PC at each RI • Mobile units at each RI • GPS clock for time synchronization at each RI
Experimental Design and Justification	The simulation at either end is started and the two systems synchronized without time delay compensation. Voltage and frequency step up and down are emulated to evaluate the accuracy of the time delay compensation method during dynamics. Target metrics are recorded for each event. The above events are repeated when time delay compensation method is turned on.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	50 μ s time step GPS Time Synchronization
Storage of experiment data	RSCAD – Various formats

Experiment Specification ES D2.2

Reference to Test Specification	TS D2.2
Title of Experiment	Characterization of Time Delay Compensation Methods in Smart Grid Application
Research Infrastructure	DPSL (Strathclyde) and RWTH Aachen?
Experiment Realisation	The use of the reduced Great Britain Power System is proposed. Three of the 5 areas of the power system will be simulated within DRTS at DPSL with remainder two at RWTH.
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DRTS with GT-Sync and GT-NET (x2) cards at each RI • DRTS Host PC at each RI • Mobile units at each RI • GPS clock for time synchronization at each RI
Experimental Design and Justification	The simulation at either end is started and the two systems synchronized with GPS based time delay compensation. A frequency event is initiated and the target measures are recorded. The above events are repeated for different time delay compensation methods.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	50 us time step GPS Time Synchronization
Storage of experiment data	RSCAD – Various formats.

Appendix 3: Demonstration 3 HTD

Test Description

Authors: A. Kontou (ICCS), T. The Hoang (CEA), E. Rikos (CRES), O. Gehrke (DTU), E. Rodriguez (TEC), A. Cortes (TEC), J. Jimeno (TEC), M. Syed (UoS), M. Opas (VTT), T.A. Zerihun (SINTEF), N. Akroud (OCT), I. Orue (OCT), I. Gilbert (OCT)

Version: 0.2

Project: ERIGrid 2.0

Name of the Test Case	Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for remote RI testing
Narrative	<p>Distribution networks are becoming increasingly “smarter”, as well as more complex, with the addition of power electronic devices, ICT, smart meters, and more. As a result, advanced control strategies to manage such networks are becoming necessary.</p> <p>Testing these systems in their entirety is becoming a challenge which is progressively accomplished by distributing parts of the system between multiple Research Infrastructures (RI) in order to cope with the increasing number of involved components and stakeholders such as grid operators, device manufactures, market participants as well as regulators. However, distributed experiments represent a challenge in itself as the coordination of interactions between these participants is an additional burden added to the already complex system under test.</p> <p>This test case aims to demonstrate tools to accelerate the setup and the coordination of such distributed experiments.</p> <p>As use case, an optimal Coordinated Voltage Control (CVC) operating as a distribution management system is chosen. The algorithm manages all the devices of the network that are capable of regulating the voltage either directly (OLTC), or through the injection of active/reactive power, such as Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) and Photovoltaic (PV) inverters. Management is based on the solution of an optimization problem, which minimizes a predefined objective function, subject to linear and non-linear constraints.</p>

	<p>Previous work has implemented this CVC algorithm in central controller installed at substation level. However, this has several drawbacks for the scope of this test case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A centralized controller is not well suited to demonstrate the benefits of the tested tools for accelerating the setup of highly distributed experiments as the controller only consists of a single instance. • A centralized controller represents a Single Point of Failure (SPoF) in the distribution grid. An outage of the controller would result in a non-optimal configuration of the system leading to increased losses and costs. At the same time, maintenance of such control systems becomes more difficult if it needs to be conducted on a live system. <p>Hence, for this test a distributed version of a Coordinated Voltage Controller is used to provide redundancy and demonstrate the capabilities of a highly distributed experimental setup. The CVC controller is initialized with all the necessary static data of the network: network topology, admittance of lines and transformer, nominal power of DERs units and storage systems, operating limits, tap change operations of the OLTC, etc. While it operates, it requests and receives real-time power measurements from the smart meters of loads and DERs units, as well as the State of Charge (SoC) of the storage systems and the current tap position of the OLTC. Using this dynamic data, it formulates the optimal power flow problem, whose objective function involves the minimization of voltage deviation of critical nodes from the nominal value, power losses of the lines and transformer, and tap change operations of the OLTC.</p>
<p>Function(s) under Investigation (Ful) the referenced specification of a function realized by the object under investigation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data-exchange for RI coupling • Deployment and configuration of SW controllers • Network Emulation for inter-controller communication • Time-synchronization • Coordinated Voltage Controller
<p>Object under Investigation (Oul) the component(s) (1..n) that are to be qualified by the test</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi IO Box (MIOB) • RlasC cluster
<p>Domain under Investigation (Dul) the relevant domains or sub-domains of test parameters and connectivity</p>	<p>Electrical Domain & ICT Domain</p>
<p>Purpose of Investigation (Pol) The test purpose in terms of Characterization, Verification, or Validation</p>	<p>The purpose of this test is the characterization of an extended research infrastructure which utilizes new tools to accelerate the setup for complex system level tests.</p>
<p>System under Test (SuT) Systems, subsystems, components included in the test case or test setup</p>	<p>PV inverter, OLTC, transformer, distribution lines, upstream network impedance, Low Voltage (LV) monitoring, DRTS</p>

Functions under Test (FuT) Functions relevant to the operation of the system under test, including FuI and relevant interactions btw. Oul and SuT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data-exchange between controllers • Data-exchange for Quasi-Static Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (QS-PHIL) interfaces • Network-emulation between controllers
Test criteria (TCR) Formulation of criteria for each Pol based on properties of SuT; encom-passes properties of test signals and output measures.	Evaluation of accuracy of the setups realized through the incorporation of the time-delay compensation methods
Target Metrics (TM) Measures required to quantify each identified test criteria	The measure required: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial setup time in person-hours • Repeated setup time in person-hours • Manual configuration effort in person-hours • Re-configuration time for SW controllers (parameter change) in seconds • Required personal resources for experiment setup (IT, Administrative, Technical, Supervisory) in number of persons.
Variability Attributes (VA) controllable or uncontrollable factors and the required variability; ref. to Pol	Variability factors include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controllable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of involved RIs – Degree of CHIL, PHIL provided by each RI vs. simulation • Uncontrollable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Communication Network conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Quality of Service * Existing Firewall and Network security Policies
Quality Attributes (QA) threshold levels for test result quality as well as the definition of a decision rule such as pass/fail criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of required manual configuration changes / adjustments is lower than X • Initial setup time lower than X hours • Repeated setup time lower than X minutes

Test Specification TS D3.1

Reference to Test Case	TC D3
Title of Test	Validation of Model, HIL Interfaces and CVC Controller

Test Rationale	This test validates the function of the CVC algorithm and the LV model and PHIL setup in three experiments. First the test setup is validated in a single RI using a single CVC instance. Afterwards the second experiment will extend the setup to multiple RIs running multiple instances of the CVC controller. This requires a data-exchange between RIs for the controller communication. Lastly, the HIL setup shall be extended to incorporate also electrical interface signals by labs contributing simulated Distributed Generation (DG) units. The integration of PHIL setups is spread across multiple RIs. Previously simulated DG units will be subsequently replaced by real lab setups involving physical PHIL setups. This test case lays the ground work to demonstrate the capabilities of the tools for providing an extended Research Infrastructure.
Specific Test System (graphical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 RTDS digital real-time simulator • 1 PB5 / Novacor Rack • 1 GTNET card with SKT protocol • N Raspberry Pi single-board computers • M simulated DG units in remote RIs or PHIL setups
Target measures	
Input and output parameters	Inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of CVC controller instances (N) • Number of coupled DG units (M)
Test Design	This initial test can be conducted fully within a single RI. A single DRTS and one or more controller instance are required and coupled via existing communication protocols like Internet Protocol (IP) or User Datagram Protocol (UDP). The CVC controllers shall be deployed via software containers on an embedded controller running Linux. The simulation of the distribution grid will be carried out on a RTDS digital real-time simulator.
Initial system state	LV-grid in steady-state, HIL interfaces deactivated, CVC controllers inactive
Evolution of system state and test signals	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Validation of measurement signal received by CVC controllers 2. Validation of successful leader election in case of a distributed setup of CVC controllers. 3. Activation of CVC controllers
Other parameters	OLTC activated/deactivated
Temporal resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DRTS simulation time-step: 50 μs • CVC cycle time: 10 s • Data-exchange rate for remote PHIL coupling: 1-10 Hz

Source of uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication network characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Latency, Packet-loss, Jitter • PHIL setups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Environmental factors: solar irradiation, wind speeds
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suspension: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Missing or incorrect measurements received by controller – Failed leader election of controller – Instabilities in LV-grid during coupling procedures of PHIL setups. • Stop: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – CVC successfully optimized system state after activation

Test Specification TS D3.2

Reference to Test Case	TC D3
Title of Test	RI Substitution
Test Rationale	This test validates the ability of the extended Research Infrastructure to quickly substitute and swap RIs in case some parts of the overall test case are unavailable due to human or physical scheduling constraints. A first experiment tests how fast and to which degree the function of one RI can be substituted by another. A second experiment tests the flexibility of the extended RI by changing the PCC at which an RI is interfaced to the larger test setup.
Specific Test System (graphical)	Same as in D3.T1
Target measures	The number of required changes made to the LV system model and the data exchange configuration.
Input and output parameters	Same as in D3.T1
Test Design	This test repeats test D3.T1 by replacing one HIL interface with another RI.
Initial system state	LV-grid in steady-state, PHIL setups coupled, CVC controllers active
Evolution of system state and test signals	Same as in D3.T1
Other parameters	Same as in D3.T1
Temporal resolution	Same as in D3.T1
Source of uncertainty	Same as in D3.T1
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Same as in D3.T1

Test Specification TS D3.3

Reference to Test Case	TC D3
Title of Test	Network Emulation
Test Rationale	The extended RI provides features such as network emulation which can be used to simulate real communication network behaviour. This test uses the network emulation functionality to reproduce contingencies in the communication network used by the OLTC and CVC controllers.
Specific Test System (graphical)	Same as in D3.T1 plus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software network-emulation for communication between CVC controller instances • Various different profiles for network emulation modelled to represent common communication networks (DSL, 4G, 5G, Fiber-Backhaul)
Target measures	Same as in D3.T1
Input and output parameters:	Same as in D3.T1
Test Design	In this test network emulation will be applied to the communication interfaces of the SW controller components such as the CVC, OLTC and LV monitoring components.
Initial system state	Same as in D3.T1
Evolution of system state and test signals	Same as in D3.T1
Other parameters	Same as in D3.T1
Temporal resolution	Same as in D3.T1
Source of uncertainty	Same as in D3.T1
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Same as in D3.T1

Test Specification TS D3.4

Reference to Test Case	TC D3
Title of Test	Repeatability and Time-to-first-Simulation
Test Rationale	A major objective of the extended RI is the acceleration of complex system level tests. This test evaluates the degree of automation which the tooling of the extended RI provides.
Specific Test System (graphical)	Same as in D3.T1
Target measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-to-first-simulation: How long does it take to setup the experiment from scratch based on an existing experiment configuration • Number of manual configuration actions: How many steps are required to performed manually as there exists no automation tooling for them?
Input and output parameters	Same as in D3.T1

Test Design	In this test network emulation will be applied to the communication interfaces of the SW controller components such as the CVC, OLTC and LV monitoring components.
Initial system state	Same as in D3.T1
Evolution of system state and test signals	Same as in D3.T1
Other parameters	Same as in D3.T1
Temporal resolution	Same as in D3.T1
Source of uncertainty	Degree of automation
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Same as in D3.T1

Appendix 4: Demonstration 4 HTD

Test Description

Authors: G. Coletta (RSE), L. Pellegrino (RES), E. Rikos (CRES), V.S. Rajkumar (TUD), M.Z. Degafa (SINTEF), O. Gehrke (DTU)

Version: 0.1

Project: ERIGrid 2.0

Name of the Test Case	Multi-Energy District Flexibility
Narrative	This test aims to investigate the power-to-heat service provision in a local multi-energy district and its impact on the electric and thermal networks. The flexibility requested by the DSO can be provided by a combination of electric and thermal storage systems as well as flexible controllable loads, such as Heat Pumps, Thermal Loads, Electric Boilers, etc.
Function(s) under Investigation (Ful) the referenced specification of a function realized (operationalized) by the object under investigation	The heating system provides services to the electrical system (a) congestion management - electrical import and export limitation; and (b) regulating power provision.
Object under Investigation (Oul) the component(s) (1..n) that are to be qualified by the test	The characterization concerns the Centralized Supervisory Controller (CSC) of a local multi-energy system.
Domain under Investigation (Dul) the relevant domains or sub-domains of test parameters and connectivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrical domain • Thermal domain • Control and ICT systems
Purpose of Investigation (Pol) The test purpose in terms of Characterization, Verification, or Validation	Verification of the impact of local flexibility on available regulating power from a local district.

<p>System under Test (SuT) Systems, subsystems, components included in the test case or test setup</p>	
<p>Functions under Test (FuT) Functions relevant to the operation of the system under test, including FuT and relevant interactions btw. Oul and SuT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P-f and Q-v control of single devices. • Local district CSC • Services provision by the CSC
<p>Test criteria (TCR) Formulation of criteria for each PoI based on properties of SuT; encompasses properties of test signals and output measures.</p>	<p>The TCR (test criteria) aims to verify the ability of the local district to provide services to the electric network:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Congestion management • Active power control at the electric network PCC • Regulating power provision
<p>Target Metrics (TM) Measures required to quantify each identified test criteria</p>	<p>The measure required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • electrical energy bound violation [MWh]: given a limit P_k^{max} of a system component $k \in K$ (e.g. power line, power transformers, electric bus, etc.) at $t \in T' \subseteq T$, measure the energy violation as: $E_k^{bound} = \sum_{t \in T'} (P_{k,t} - P_k^{max})^+$ • electrical energy balance deviation [MWh]: given a set point P_{PCC}^{set} at the electric network PCC at $t \in T' \subseteq T$, measure the energy violation as: $E_{set} = \sum_{t \in T'} P_{PCC,t} - P_{PCC,t}^{set}$

Variability Attributes (VA) controllable or uncontrollable factors and the required variability; ref. to PoI	Controllable factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • heat pumps set-point • electrical and thermal storage system set-point Uncontrollable factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demand (electrical and thermal) • PV generation
Quality Attributes (QA) threshold levels for test result quality as well as the definition of a decision rule such as pass/fail criteria	n/a

Qualification Strategy

The PoI is addressed through the implementation of a single Test Specification (TS1), which includes multiple RIs. A first phase (ES1) will verify the ERIGrid 2.0 extended research infrastructure capability and set-up the main experiments:

- ES2: Congestion management
- ES3: Active power control at the electric network PCC
- ES4: Regulating power provision

Test Specification TS D4.1

Reference to Test Case	TC D4
Title of Test	CSC service provision verification.
Test Rationale	This test verifies the local district operation seeking to demonstrate that the CSC respond to a service request: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Congestion management • Active power control at the electric network PCC • Regulating power provision

Specific Test System
(graphical)

The system under test includes an electrical system, a district heating system and a control system. Each is sketched below.

Thermal system

The thermal system is composed by two subsystems, one connected to a District Heating Network (DHN) and interfaced to the electrical system through a Combine Heat and Power (CHP) and another one fed by an Electrical Heat Pump (EHP).

Electrical system

The electrical system is composed by three main physical feeders and a simulated grid portion. The physical feeders connect a simulated BESS, a CHP and an EHP.

	<p>Control domain coupling</p> <p>Control system which determines the set-points for the controllable resources in order to provide the requested services.</p>
Target measures	<i>See Test Case Template.</i>
Input and output parameters	<p>Input:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrical PCC voltage and frequency. • Set-point of the requested services. • Non programmable generation and demand profiles. <p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy fluxes in the electrical and thermal networks [kW] • State of the electrical and thermal networks (in terms of voltage, current, injected active and reactive power, temperature, pressure, etc.)
Test Design	<p>The test comprises three experiments, 2 hours of district operation each.</p> <p>During these 2 hours, in each experiment the CSC keeps the temperature at each load in a range from 70 °C to 90 °C, while one of these services to the electrical network is provided:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Congestion management • Active power control at the electric network PCC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – for 09:30 to 10:00, keep district electrical consumption below P_{import}^{limit} [kW]. – for 10:00 to 10:30, keep district electrical consumption above P_{export}^{limit} [kW]. – for 10:30 to 11:00, keep district electrical consumption below P_{import}^{limit} [kW]. • Regulating power provision <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – for 17:00 to 18:00, keep district electrical consumption equal to P_{set} [kW].
Initial system state	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • each component is initialized to the state given in the associated dataset. • the battery and thermal storage state of charge is set to 50% of their nominal energy. • The thermal set-point of the CHP is such that its delivery temperature is T_{CHP}^{set} [°C].
Evolution of system state and test signals	<p>The thermal system serves real-world load, that will be considered as exogenous disturbances. The thermal PCC temperature and pressure are considered as exogenous variables as well. The electrical loads, except the EHP, and the electrical generation, except the CHP, are simulated based on predetermined profiles.</p>
Other parameters	n/a
Temporal resolution	The test is run at a fixed time step of 15 min.

Source of uncertainty	Since the exact electrical demand signal consists of a deterministic trend and a randomized factor, each “run” above should be repeated 10 times, with the mean and standard deviation of each target metric recorded.
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	n/a

Mapping to Research Infrastructure

The test specifications are implemented in several Quasi-Static PHIL (QS-PHIL) experiments in order to exploit them geographically separated over several research facilities.

Experiment Specification ES D4.1

Reference to Test Specification	TS D4.1
Title of Experiment	Experimental Test Case and extended research infrastructure validation
Research Infrastructure	RSE, CRES, DTU, TUD, SINTEF
Experiment Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hardware interfaces • ICT interfaces design and implementation • Overall system functions validation
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<p>Heat Pump (CRES):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nominal capacity (electrical): $S=18\text{ kVA}$, $P=16\text{ kW}$ • Controllable variables: Operating state (on-off) • Measurement points: Active (kW)/Reactive (kVAr)/Apparent power (kVA), Active (kWh)/Reactive (kVArh) energy, Voltage (Line-to-line and Line-to-neutral) (V), Frequency (Hz), Indoor Temperature at 3 different points (oC) • Normal operating conditions: Indoor temperature $18 \div 22^\circ$ • Maximum operating limits: Indoor temperature $15 \div 25^\circ$

- Interfacing with other RIs: Currently, all measurements are collected and published on the Internet via an eWon 4001 datalogger, which is accessible in the following IP address: 195.251.43.80 (username and password are required). The current data resolution setting is 5min (averaging values) but higher sampling resolution is possible (eWon provides instantaneous values as well).

Heat network (DTU):

- Coupling device is a stack of 9 electrical flow heaters of 2.5 kW each (22.5 kW total) which can be individually controlled through semiconductor relays. The heaters feed into a 200l accumulator tank. The device can operate as a constant-power source by controlling the discharge of the tank via a remote-controllable feed pump.
- Each of the lines E1, E2 has a length of about 400 m (=1600m total for two lines w/ forward and return circuit each)
- The load in the middle of the line is the controllable heating system (water-to-air heat exchangers) of a laboratory hall.
- The load at the end of the line is a controllable heat dumpload.
- Measurements at each bay: T_{forward}, T_{return} flow, differential pressure
- Distributed temperature measurements (forward+return) along each line, every 100 m.

	<p>CHP (RSE):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CHP plant with a NG Internal combustion engine (50 kWe, 81 kWth); • 1 Bidirectional DC/AC Front-end-converter (30 kVA) • 1 Bidirectional B2B converter (30 kVA) • Three-phase LV grid
<p>Experimental Design and Justification</p>	<p>This test case aims to validate the capability of the extended research infrastructure for real-world multi-energy system experiments. The use of the extended research infrastructure increases the reality of the experiment by including real components and real-world user behavior.</p>
<p>Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty</p>	<p>The diagram illustrates the multi-domain experimental setup. It features several interconnected components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SINTEF: Includes an OPAL-RT real-time simulator, BESS (emulation), and a 200 kVA EGSION converter. TUD: A Distributor Grid Simulator connected to the SINTEF setup. RSE: A Real-time Simulation Environment containing a Grid-forming Converter, Grid-following Converter, and a Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit. DTU: A Data Transfer Unit with two counters (Counter 1 and Counter 2) and two load sources (Load power source and Load lamp source). CRES: A Combined Real-time Experimentation System including a Water tank, Heat pump, Fan Coil 1, and Fan Coil 10. A legend at the bottom left identifies the domains: blue for Electrical Domain, red for Thermal Domain, and yellow for Facilities. </p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M1: Active power and voltage magnitude at the SINTEF facility; • M2: Active power and voltage magnitude at the RSE facility; <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Quantity</th> <th colspan="3">% Full Scale</th> </tr> <tr> <th>0-5 %</th> <th>5-20 %</th> <th>20-100 %</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Voltage</td> <td colspan="3">0.20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Current</td> <td>3.03%</td> <td>1.55 %</td> <td>1.08 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Active Power</td> <td>3.06%</td> <td>1.62 %</td> <td>1.17 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Reactive Power</td> <td>3.19 %</td> <td>1.86 %</td> <td>1.48 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Apparent Power</td> <td>3.06%</td> <td>1.62 %</td> <td>1.17 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Frequency</td> <td colspan="3">± 0.10 mHz</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M3: CHP active power (RSE); Same (M2) • M4: EHP active power (CRES); – Precision=0.01 kW • M5-M7: Temperature and mass flow (DTU); • M6: CHP Temperature and mass flow (RSE); – Mass flow Accuracy: ± 0.5 kg/s – Temperature Accuracy: ± 0.2 K • M8-M9: Temperature and mass flow (CRES); – Temperature precision = 0.1 °C 	Quantity	% Full Scale			0-5 %	5-20 %	20-100 %	Voltage	0.20%			Current	3.03%	1.55 %	1.08 %	Active Power	3.06%	1.62 %	1.17 %	Reactive Power	3.19 %	1.86 %	1.48 %	Apparent Power	3.06%	1.62 %	1.17 %	Frequency	± 0.10 mHz		
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Reactive Power	3.19 %	1.86 %	1.48 %																													
Apparent Power	3.06%	1.62 %	1.17 %																													
Frequency	± 0.10 mHz																															
Storage of experiment data	Data of each facility will be stored in a separate database at the experiment temporal resolution with a common temporal reference.																															

Experiment Specification ES D4.2

Reference to Test Specification	TS D4.1
Title of Experiment	Congestion management
Research Infrastructure	RSE, CRES, DTU, TUD, SINTEF
Experiment Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial conditions definition • Control system implementation • Experiment execution
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	See ES D4.1
Experimental Design and Justification	This test case aims to demonstrate the ability of a multi-energy district to solve or mitigate congestion on the electric power distribution network.

Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<i>See ES D4.1</i>
Storage of experiment data	<i>See ES D4.1</i>

Experiment Specification ES D4.3

Reference to Test Specification	TS D4.1
Title of Experiment	Active power control at the electric network PCC.
Research Infrastructure	RSE, CRES, DTU, TUD, SINTEF
Experiment Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial conditions definition • Control system implementation • Experiment execution
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<i>See ES D4.1</i>
Experimental Design and Justification	This test case aims to demonstrate the ability of a multi-energy district to limit power absorption at the electric network PCC.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<i>See ES D4.1</i>
Storage of experiment data	<i>See ES D4.1</i>

Experiment Specification ES D4.4

Reference to Test Specification	TS D4.1
Title of Experiment	Balancing power provision.
Research Infrastructure	RSE, CRES, DTU, TUD, SINTEF
Experiment Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial conditions definition • Control system implementation • Experiment execution
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<i>See ES D4.1</i>
Experimental Design and Justification	This test case aims to demonstrate the ability of a multi-energy district to provide fixed power at the electric network PCC.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<i>See ES D4.1</i>

Storage of experiment data	<i>See ES D4.1</i>
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Appendix 5: Demonstration 5 HTD

Test Description

Authors: T.A. Zerihun (SINTEF), O. Gehrke (DTU)

Version: 0.1

Project: ERIGrid 2.0

Name of the Test Case	Demo 5
Narrative	<p>Smart grids have become complex system of systems characterized by mutual interactions and interdependence between the power system and the ICT systems. To evaluate the system level integration and validation of such a system, proper attention should be focused on the design of the simulation tool, that can simulate the two systems holistically. So far, there is no established cyber-physical approach/software tools for designing, analyzing, and validating smart grid systems sufficiently in such manner.</p> <p>The lack of such system validation for smart grids is addressed by the European ERIGrid 2.0 project where a co-simulation based approach is developed. The software co-simulation in ERIGrid is realized by employing the Mosaik framework as a co-simulation master and interfacing all simulators (AC, ICT and controller) via the Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) standard. The aim of this test case is to characterize the achievable accuracy of this simulation approach. To achieve this, simulation results will be compared to hardware-based laboratory tests.</p> <p>The case assumes a section of an electrical distribution grid, multiple (≥ 2) aggregators that operate independently of each other. Each of the aggregators maintains a portfolio of flexible DERs units that can provide on-demand delivery of a grid service (e.g. load reduction/production increase). The primary customer for the grid service is assumed to be the local DSO where a dispatch unit is tasked with continuously matching the service demand indicated by the DSO, and to submit service activation requests to the appropriate aggregators.</p> <p>During the simulation, a communication fault (either temporary or permanent) disrupts communication between the dispatch unit and one of the aggregators. To ensure that the service demand is met, the dispatch unit must</p>
	<p>arrange to meet the service demand with the remaining aggregator(s). It is assumed that an aggregator affected by a communication fault will continue to deliver the service agreed upon. However, due to the lack of updates from the dispatch unit, these services will eventually diverge from the evolving needs of the grid.</p> <p>The purpose of the test is to characterize the performance of the simulator coupling in a co-simulation setup, rather than the performance of the individual domain simulators. Therefore, two points must be observed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The simulated system must exhibit a strong enough (and ideally closed-loop) coupling between the individual domains • While applying variations to input parameters during the characterization test, known corner cases for the individual domain simulators should be avoided, to prevent in-domain inaccuracies to shadow for intra-domain inaccuracies.

<p>Function(s) under Investigation (Ful) the referenced specification of a function realized (operationalized) by the object under investigation</p>	<p>Multi-domain simulation of coupled AC+ICT systems, consisting of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrical network simulation • Communication network simulation • Simulator coupling/integration
<p>Object under Investigation (Oul) the component(s) (1..n) that are to be qualified by the test</p>	<p>AC/ICT cosimulation setup, consisting of a power system simulator, a communication network simulator, a simulator coupling framework and a cosimulation master algorithm. The investigation is specifically focusing on the performance of the cosimulation setup, not on that of the simulated system.</p>
<p>Domain under Investigation (Dul) the relevant domains or sub-domains of test parameters and connectivity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrical domain • ICT
<p>Purpose of Investigation (Pol) The test purpose in terms of Characterization, Verification, or Validation</p>	<p>Characterization of the properties of the cosimulation framework by comparing the dynamics of the simulated system to the dynamics of a comparable physical (laboratory) setup. This is the first step towards a validation test, by exploring the range of achievable performance. The data collected would allow a reference scale (pass/fail) to be developed at a later time.</p>
<p>System under Test (SuT) Systems, subsystems, components included in the test case or test setup</p>	<p>The SuT consists of the Oul (AC/ICT cosimulation) plus the simulated multi-domain system. The latter consists of an electrical grid section, energy resources, aggregators, a dispatch unit, a service requester (DSO) and an ICT command and control infrastructure. The electrical grid section is a part of a LV and/or Medium Voltage (MV) distribution grid (e.g. 0.4kV and 10kV) with a number of flexible DERs units distributed across one or multiple feeders. The ICT infrastructure includes three separate control entities (dispatch unit, aggregator and DERs controller) as well as a wide area communication network between these entities.</p>
<p>Functions under Test (FuT) Functions relevant to the operation of the system under test, including Ful and relevant interactions btw. Oul and SuT</p>	<p>The FuT consists of the Ful (Multi-domain simulation of coupled AC+ICT systems) as well as the following functions of the simulated system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication fault detection and impact mitigation • Coordinated congestion management, consisting of an algorithm for congestion management as well as the communication between units needed to implement the algorithm (i.e. between unit controllers and aggregators and between aggregators and dispatch unit) • Aggregator internal dispatch mechanism, consisting of portfolio management and unit dispatch • Unit controller functionality, consisting of local flexibility calculation and management • A dispatch mechanism for aggregators, executing on the dispatch unit. • A congestion detection method, emulating the determination of service requirements by a DSO.

<p>Test criteria (TCR) Formulation of criteria for each PoI based on properties of SuT; encompasses properties of test signals and output measures.</p>	<p>The expected accuracy of the simulation is currently unknown in relation to a laboratory setup. Therefore, the test focuses on a quantification of the accuracy, and to identify factors influencing the achievable accuracy. A challenge in determining overall accuracy are the strongly different time scales of the two domains. The test criteria are therefore designed to compare overall system performance rather than the performance of subsystems or individual domains.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TCR1: Deviation of service delivered from service requested (long-term performance) • TCR2: Time to restore steady-state operation after a failure event in the communication domain (nonresponsive aggregator) • TCR3: Time to restore steady-state operation after a failure event in the electrical domain (failure of controllable resource)
<p>Target Metrics (TM) Measures required to quantify each identified test criteria</p>	<p>TCR1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall integral error [kWh] • Maximum overall service deviation [kW] • Mean overall service deviation [kW] • Maximum individual integral error [kWh] • Maximum individual service deviation [kW] <p>TCR2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time from occurrence to detection of communication failure [ms] • Time from detection of communication failure to end of distribution of new setpoints to unit controllers [ms] • Time from reception of new setpoints at unit controllers to (physical) service restoration [ms] <p>TCR3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time from occurrence to detection of electrical equipment failure [ms] • Time from detection of electrical equipment failure to end of distribution of new setpoints to unit controllers [ms] • Time from reception of new setpoints at unit controllers to (physical) service restoration [ms]
<p>Variability Attributes (VA) controllable or uncontrollable factors and the required variability; ref. to PoI</p>	<p>Controllable factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of communication failure [100 ms to permanent] • Variability of baseload profile [0 to 100% of mean baseload] • Round-trip communication latency in the wide-area sections of the network [10...200 ms]
<p>Quality Attributes (QA) threshold levels for test result quality as well as the definition of a decision rule such as pass/fail criteria</p>	<p>Confidence in the accuracy and synchronicity of time measurements (accuracy better than 1 ms, clock synchronicity better than 100 μs)</p>

Figure 7: Structure demo.

Qualification strategy

- The simulated system can be excited in two ways, by events (e.g. equipment failure or limit violations) on the communication side or by events on the electrical network side. It is assumed that both types of events need to be tested against since they will result in different dynamics due to the unequal strength of the domain coupling between the two simulated domains. The differences in the setup for the triggering event require two different test specifications.
- Each test will require two experiments – one with a simulated system, and the other one with a physical lab setup. This results in a total of four experiment specifications.

Test Specification TS D5.1

Reference to Test Case	TC-17
Title of Test	Communication failure
Test Rationale	The test will establish the performance of the multi-aggregator system simulated by the co-simulation setup in comparison to the physical system test of a similar setup, when a communication failure is introduced. The communication failure will disrupt the flow of information between one of the aggregators and the dispatch unit.
Specific Test System (graphical)	

Target measures	<p>Active power measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $P_{r,i}(t)$ as the requested service and • $P_{d,i}(t)$ as the delivered service for each network segment $i = 1..n$: <p>Time measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T0: the time of occurrence of a failure event • T1: Time at which new service requests are generated • T2: Time at which new setpoints are sent/received
Input and output parameters:	<p>Input:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Load profile (time series) • Communication delay and jitter <p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active power and time measurements
Test Design	<p>The system starts with stable operation where the generation matches the consumptions.</p> <p>A small variation of the dynamic load is introduced that requires the dispatch and aggregators to respond by sending new service request/setpoints to the DERs controllers.</p> <p>A communication system failure is initiated, and the target measures will be recorded until a new equilibrium point is reached. This may be repeated for different type and location of faults.</p> <p>The above process/test will be conducted using both co-simulation and hardware-based experiments.</p>
Initial system state	The system is initialised where the loads are kept constant, and no failure is introduced to the power or ICT system.
Evolution of system state and test signals	<p>The system starts with its initial stage as presented above.</p> <p>At T1 and onwards, a small variation in the dynamic load is introduced that will continually initiate new service requests from the dispatch to the aggregators and new setpoints from aggregators to DERs controllers.</p> <p>At T2, to initiate more interaction between ICT and power system, a communication system triggering event/failure is introduced by removing one of the line of communication between the dispatch and aggregators.</p>
Other parameters	Communication delay, time to resend service requests or frequency of heartbeat signals (between Dispatch - Aggregator - DERs controller)
Temporal resolution	0.1 ms for ICT and 1 s for Power system
Source of uncertainty	n/a
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Stopping criteria: Elapsed time (fixed length experiment)

Test Specification TS D5.2

Reference to Test Case	TC-17
Title of Test	Grid event/power system failure

<p>Test Rationale</p>	<p>The test will establish the performance of the multi-aggregator system simulated by the co-simulation setup in comparison to the physical system test of a similar setup, when a power system disturbance event/ failure is introduced. The grid disturbance event can be either a sudden increase in demand or a power system failure which will be large enough to require a rescheduling action by the dispatch/aggregator system in order to ensure continued delivery of the service.</p>
<p>Specific Test System (graphical)</p>	
<p>Target measures</p>	<p>Active power measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $P_{r,i}(t)$ as the requested service and • $P_{d,i}(t)$ as the delivered service for each network segment $i = 1..n$: <p>Time measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T_0: the time of occurrence of a failure event • T_1: Time at which new service requests are generated • T_2: Time at which new setpoints are sent/received
<p>Input and output parameters</p>	<p>Input:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Load profile (time series) • Communication delay and jitter <p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active power and time measurements
<p>Test Design</p>	<p>The system starts with stable operation where the generation matches the consumptions. A power system disturbance event / failure is initiated, and the target measures will be recorded until a new equilibrium point is reached. This may be repeated for different type and location of faults. The above process/test will be conducted using both co-simulation and hardware-based experiments.</p>
<p>Initial system state</p>	<p>The system is initialized where the loads are kept constant, and no failure is introduced to the power or ICT system.</p>
<p>Evolution of system state and test signals</p>	<p>The system starts with its initialized. At t_1, to initiate more interaction between ICT and power system, a power system triggering event/failure is introduced by adding a load to emulate loss of supply/generation.</p>
<p>Other parameters</p>	<p>Communication delay, time to resend service requests or frequency of heartbeat signals (between Dispatch - Aggregator - DERs controller)</p>

Temporal resolution	1 ms
Source of uncertainty	n/a
Suspension criteria / Stopping criteria	Stopping criteria: Elapsed time (fixed length experiment)

Experiment Specification ES D5.1

Reference to Test Specification	TS #1 – D5.1
Title of Experiment	Simulated system, communication failure
Research Infrastructure	NSGL (SINTEF) and Syslab (DTU)
Experiment Realisation	The simulation will be realized using the Mosaik 3 and FMI 3 based co-simulation framework developed in ERIGRID 2 - JRA 2. The test will be conducted on one machine (PC) where all the power and ICT simulators, control functions and the Mosaik framework runs.
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	The power system is simulated and the ICT will be simulated using NS3. FMI3 will be used for interfacing the power and ICT simulators and Mosaik for an orchestration. The control algorithms will be implemented in python within the Mosaik framework.
Experimental Design and Justification	The test will establish the performance of the multi-aggregator system as simulated by the co-simulation setup, when a communication failure is introduced. The communication failure will disrupt the flow of information between one of the aggregators and the dispatch unit.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquisition time and jitter of delay measurements
Storage of experiment data	n/a

Experiment Specification ES D5.2

Reference to Test Specification	TS #1 – D5.1
Title of Experiment	Physical system, communication failure
Research Infrastructure	NSGL (SINTEF) and Syslab (DTU)
Experiment Realisation	It will be a single RI experiment where the whole system will be implemented in hardware and/ partly emulation in each laboratory.

Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LV distribution grid in NSGL or Syslab • Measurement instruments - (CT/PT, MUs) • The dispatch and aggregator controllers will be implemented as Python algorithms running on a PC • IEC 61850 based communication for collecting measurements from the distribution grid • An emulation of the Wide Area Network (WAN) using mininet will be used for the communication between measurement units to DSO dispatch, DSO dispatch to aggregators and aggregators to DERs controllers.
Experimental Design and Justification	The test will establish the performance of the multi-aggregator system as simulated by the co-simulation setup, when a communication failure is introduced. The communication failure will disrupt the flow of information between one of the aggregators and the dispatch unit.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition time and jitter of electrical grid measurements in the laboratory • Setpoint keeping precision of DERs components in the laboratory
Storage of experiment data	n/a

Experiment Specification ES D5.3

Reference to Test Specification	TS #1 – D5.2
Title of Experiment	Simulated system, grid event
Research Infrastructure	NSGL (SINTEF) and Syslab (DTU)
Experiment Realisation	The simulation will be realized using the Mosaik 3 and FMI 3 based co-simulation framework developed in ERIGRID 2 - JRA 2. The test will be conducted on one machine (PC) where all the power and ICT simulators, control functions and the Mosaik framework runs.
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	The power system is simulated and the ICT will be simulated using NS3. FMI3 will be used for interfacing the power and ICT simulators and Mosaik for an orchestration. The control algorithms will be implemented in python within the Mosaik framework
Experimental Design and Justification	The test will establish the performance of the multi-aggregator system as simulated by the co-simulation setup, when a power disturbance event is introduced. The power disturbance event will trigger a rescheduling action by the dispatch/aggregator system in order to ensure continued delivery of the service.
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition time and jitter of delay measurements
Storage of experiment data	n/a

Experiment Specification ES D5.4

Reference to Test Specification	TS #1 – D5.2
Title of Experiment	Physical system, grid event
Research Infrastructure	NSGL (SINTEF) and Syslab (DTU)
Experiment Realisation	It will be a single RI experiment where the whole system will be implemented in hardware and/ partly emulation in each laboratory.
Experiment Setup (concrete lab equipment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LV distribution grid in NSGL or Syslab • Measurement instruments - (CT/PT, MUs) • The dispatch and aggregator controllers will be implemented as Python algorithms running on a PC • IEC 61850 based communication for collecting measurements from the distribution grid • An emulation of the WAN using mininet will be used for the communication between measurement units to DSO dispatch, DSO dispatch to aggregators and aggregators to DERs controllers.
Experimental Design and Justification	The test will establish the performance of the multi-aggregator system as simulated by the co-simulation setup, when a power disturbance event is introduced. The power disturbance event will trigger a rescheduling action by the dispatch/aggregator system in order to ensure continued delivery of the service
Precision of equipment and measurement uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition time and jitter of electrical grid measurements in the laboratory • Setpoint keeping precision of DERs components in the laboratory
Storage of experiment data	n/a

Consortium

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